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Open access books: a modern way of publishing

– Gwyn Bevan

Technology enhances research. It enables academics to work and publish openly, access more material and more quickly, and reach a wider audience.

The research landscape has changed dramatically during Gwyn Bevan's time in academia, including how and where academics publish and why. Bevan, Emeritus Professor of Policy Analysis in the Department of Management at the London School of Economics and Political Science, welcomes those changes. He says the benefits are immense – to academics, to research, to academia and to society more generally.

How research used to happen

Bevan published his first book in 1980, on healthcare. Back then, academics had to buy books to access research or travel to libraries.

He said:

“If you wanted to get an article, you'd have to go to a library and photocopy it. It was a very laborious process.”

Digitisation changes everything

With the advent of the Internet, digitisation and more latterly, open access publishing, Bevan says everything has become a lot simpler and a lot quicker. And academics can draw on more material than ever before.

He added:

“So much is available electronically now – it’s transformational. You’re able to get access to original documents, including documents published in the early 20th century.”

Publishing today

Bevan recently published his first book open access with LSE Press – How Did Britain Come to This? His university advised publishing open access and met the publishing costs. Bevan has been delighted at the attention it has received, having notched up over 3000 downloads in the first nine months.

This experience has led Bevan to conclude that academics who publish open access gain far more visibility for themselves and their work, boosting their profile and impact. He believes making research freely and easily available will lead to higher readership numbers and higher citation numbers. He said:

“ What happens is that stuff you can access electronically will get read and cited, and stuff which you have to buy as a book or go to a library or access behind a paywall, will not do anywhere near as well and will not have the same reach or citations.

How was publishing open access different?

Bevan discovered that the process was very similar to traditional publishing, although he did have to spend a lot of time including links and checking that they worked. Although it was time consuming, Bevan said it was worth the effort because links are useful, making research outputs stronger. And on the flip side, having an electronic publication meant there was no need for him to provide an index because of all the links.

Taking research beyond academia

Bevan's book discusses governance in the UK, exploring the current state of public services, neoliberalism, privatisation, housing, healthcare and so on. The book was not written for the benefit of Bevan's academic colleagues - they are not his target audience. He wanted to write a book that appealed to everyone, particularly people outside of academia. The idea was to make academic principles and concepts accessible to the general public, both through publishing open access and through clear, jargon-free content.